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Executive summary

This document provides an overview of the EDEN ISS design pertaining to the structural elements and mechanisms within the MTF. In particular, this document describes the design of the two containers and the external mechanical interfaces, as well as the internal configuration within the Service Section container and the Future Exploration Greenhouse container.

The MTF outer structure consists of two modified 20 foot high cube shipping containers. The modifications to the standard containers concern the insulation needed for thermal control of the facility, mounting interfaces for equipment installed external to the MTF and the raised floor construction within the containers, among other aspects.

The internal design of the MTF is presented in two parts, each pertaining to one of the containers. The Service Section container internal structural design consists of a rack structure, built using ITEM profiles, which houses air management, nutrient delivery and thermal subsystem components. Similarly, a cabinet is included in the cold porch for storage of, for example, crew clothing. To provide a comfortable working environment for crew members accessing the MTF, noise reduction panels have been installed on the ITEM rack.

As with the Service Section container internal design, the Future Exploration Greenhouse internal structural design consists of an ITEM profile rack and a number of mechanical interfaces for installation of various subsystem components.

This document also covers the design of the Elevated Platform, on which the MTF containers will be mounted in the Antarctic.

Aside from the design description, this document also details the actions which need to be taken in the course of nominal operations, as well as some lessons learned for future design and development efforts.

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Acronyms

Acronym	Explanation
EP	Elevated Platform
FEG	Future Exploration Greenhouse
MTF	Mobile Test Facility
NM-III	Neumayer III Station
SS	Service Section

1 Top-level design overview

The Mobile Test Facility (MTF) consists of two 20 foot containers, to be connected in-situ in the Antarctic, and mounted on an Elevated Platform (EP), as shown in Figure 1-1. The decision to use two 20 foot shipping containers was made to comply with the existing logistics chain to and from the Antarctic. One of the containers will be utilized as a Future Exploration Greenhouse (FEG), while the other container will house the Service Section and a Cold Porch.

Figure 1-1: Concept drawing of the Mobile Test Facility mounted on the platform.

Figure 1-2 below gives a schematic view of the MTF, with labels indicating the different sections.

Figure 1-2: Schematic representation of the important areas of the MTF.

In this chapter, the design of the platform and of the containers will be presented. Subsequently, in chapters 2 and 3 the internal configuration of, respectively, the Service Section container and the Future Exploration Greenhouse container, will be discussed.

1.1 Elevated Platform

The Elevated Platform, shown being assembled near the Neumayer III station (NM-III) in Figure 1-3, is based on an existing platform design which is used for the Spuso Air Chemistry Observatory near NM-III. The platform provides between 1-2 meters of clearance between the containers and the ground, to prevent the facility from being covered in snow and ice. To accommodate the yearly build-up of snow, the platform is raised each year and the platform can be extended, when necessary, to allow the platform to be raised further throughout the years of operation.

Figure 1-3: Elevated Platform being assembled in the Antarctic (Credit: Pitt Eder)

The design of the EP, shown in detail in the technical drawings in Appendix A, consists of stairs to climb onto the platform. The containers are mounted on twist-locks which are then welded into place onto the main load-bearing profiles in the center section of the platform. Around this center section, grating provides a walkway for crew to circle around the facility. Railings running around the length of the platform provide safety for the crew, preventing them from slipping and falling off.

1.2 Service Section container

The Service Section container, as indicated in Figure 1-2, houses the Cold Porch and the Service Section. It holds the subsystem components needed to maintain the environment within the FEG and provides space for crew to change, as well as work.

1.2.1 Container External design

West-facing surface

The main entrance to the MTF is located on the West-facing side of the Service Section container, see Figure 1-4. Both the main access door and the emergency exit door open outwards and door stops are installed on the outside of the containers to prevent the doors from swinging open too far. Above the door, threaded holes enable the installation of a door light, as well as an observation camera, via bolts. Additionally, a cable channel will be mounted above the door. This channel will run along all sides of the Service Section and Future Exploration Greenhouse and provides protection from the harsh environment for the cables which need to be connected to external components, such as the lights. Mounting holes are also positioned next to the door, providing a mechanical interface for a ladder to allow rooftop access.

As will be discussed in more detail later, the MTF has a raised floor, which resulted in the need for a step ladder on the outside of the container.

Figure 1-4: Main entrance to the MTF

North-facing surface

The North-facing side of the container faces towards the Neumayer III station. A window has been incorporated into the container on this side. The window is approximately 1700 by 800 mm and triple-glazed to minimize heat loss from the facility.

Six lamps, three on the Service Section container and three on the FEG container, are installed on this side to provide illumination of the external platform, as well as the logo which has been applied to the container sides. Additionally, there are two interfaces between the container exterior and interior through which cables will be run. A GK-Packsystem modular marine packing system (GK Marine, 2015) was selected as the most suitable candidate for this interface. This system has been proven within the Antarctic environment through use on the Air Chemistry Observatory at NM-III. The GK system consists of a steel or aluminium frame which is welded into place at the point where the cables or pipes need to penetrate through the container wall. The frame is filled with rubber block elements to pre-determined sizes. As the cables and pipes are placed through the frame, gaps are filled up by these rubber blocks which are then pressed together with a wedge seal to achieve water and gas tightness. Examples of such systems are shown in Figure 1-5.

Figure 1-5: Water and gas tight GK-Packsystem interfaces on ships.

One of the interfaces will provide an access point for the main power and data cables from Neumayer III, while the other is used to run cables from the power and data systems to the externally mounted components (e.g. the lamps).

South-facing surface

The South side of the Service Section container has a cable channel running along its length, as well as mounting holes for fixation of a light. Additionally, it has a mounting bracket to hold CO₂-cylinders, each with a capacity of 13 Litres. Additional mounting holes, for fixation of some of the gas delivery system components, are positioned close to the CO₂-cylinders, see Figure 1-6.

Furthermore, this side of the container will also have an opening leading into the container, for the air inlet of the Surface Section. In addition to this, a GK-Packsystem interface is located on this side to allow CO₂ lines to enter the facility and to facilitate a piping connection between the internal thermal management system and the roof-mounted free cooler, see Figure 1-6.

To protect the piping and CO₂ regulator equipment from the harsh environment, a metal cover will be mounted over these elements.

Figure 1-6: (Left) CO2 bottles and regulator panels on the South side of the MTF. (Right) CAD image of the roof-mounted free cooler and thermal piping connections

East-facing surface

The East-facing surface of the Service Section container has been removed. This side of the container will be connected with the West-facing side of the Future Exploration Greenhouse container in-situ in the Antarctic. During transport this side will be sealed with an easily removable covering, to ensure the container is protected from external conditions and contamination.

Roof

The roof of the container will have mounting interfaces to attach the safety cage, which will provide additional protection to crew members climbing or descending the stairs.

To ensure crew members cannot fall of the roof, a safety railing has been installed on the roof. Crew members will hook onto this system with a tether, which will prevent them from slipping off the sides, while still allowing them full access to all areas of the roof.

Finally, the roof will also accommodate two I-beams on which the heat rejection unit, called a free cooler, will be mounted. Additionally, there will be a mounting interface on one of the I-beams for installation of a pole. This pole will serve as a mounting point for a patch antenna, which will be facing towards the Neumayer III station.

1.2.2 Container Internal design

Insulation and internal surfaces

Based on thermal analysis it was decided that 80 mm thickness of poly-urethane insulation material should be incorporated into the walls and roof of the container. The insulation is shielded with a foil, to prevent moisture from penetrating the insulation material. This foil, in turn, will be covered by 10 mm thick high pressure laminate 'Trespa' plates, which will form the actual internal walls of the container.

To meet the structural requirements and allow for fixation of components, 40x40x5 mm and 40x60x5 mm profiles will be built into the walls, forming a structural connection between the Trespa plates and mounted equipment and the corrugated outer walls of the container. A section view of the wall design can be seen in Figure 1-7.

Figure 1-7: Wall and ceiling structure design

On pre-defined locations, plywood plates are integrated into the walls to accommodate mounting of heavier components, such as the Command and Data Handling System (CDHS) Argus box.

The design for the container bottom is slightly different, see Figure 1-8. The space at the bottom of the container, which is typically empty, aside from structural C-profiles, has been filled up with polyurethane foam, with a minimum density of 40 kg/m³. On top of this insulation, and the C-profiles, is the standard container floor.

Figure 1-8: Floor structure design

Raised floor structure and basin

On top of the standard container floor, the raised floor structure and basin are installed. Additionally, a removable fresh-water and waste-water tank have been placed underneath the raised floor in the Cold Porch area.

The basin consists of thin steel sheets, welded together to form a water-tight reservoir, which will capture any fluid leakages. The raised floor structure has been incorporated into the container to provide a separated space for air ducts and fluid lines. The floor itself has removable panels and profiles, to allow access to the sub-floor space for installation and maintenance. The raised floor is approximately 30 cm above the actual container floor and the free height for the ducts and fluid lines is about 25 cm.

Figure 1-9: Service Section Container – Floor structure

Figure 1-9 provides an overview of the structural profiles making up the raised floor structure in the Service Section container. The green line in this image depicts a separation wall between the Service Section area and the Cold Porch. The pink dots indicate the mounting points for the different subsystems and components.

Separation wall

To create the desired separation between the cold porch and the Service Section, an additional wall has been built into the container. This separation wall has an access door to the Service Section, as well as openings for an air duct, a cable channel and several fluid lines, as can be seen in Figure 1-10.

Figure 1-10: Cold Porch – Service Section separation wall

1.3 Future Exploration Greenhouse container

The Future Exploration Greenhouse (FEG) container encompasses the main plant cultivation area of the MTF.

1.3.1 Container External design

West-facing surface

The West-facing surface of the FEG container has been removed. This side will be connected to the East-facing side of the Service Section container. Again, this side will be sealed with easily removable covering during transport.

North-facing surface

The North-facing surface of this container has mounting interfaces for three external lamps, which will illuminate the elevated platform, as well as the logo.

South-facing surface

The South-facing surface has no external interfaces, aside from the external cable channel which runs along the upper edge of the MTF.

East-facing surface

The East-facing side of this container, see Figure 1-11, contains the emergency exit door with door-stops, the cable channel, a mounting interface for a lamp, as well as a step ladder.

Figure 1-11: MTF emergency exit

Roof

The only item installed on the roof of the FEG is a security system, to prevent crew from falling off of the container. During the initial build-up of the facility, the crew will likely need to be on the roof of this container to run cables through the cable channels to the various wall-mounted components. To ensure a safe working environment, a safety system is required.

1.3.2 Container Internal design

The internal design of the two containers will be almost identical. As such, only the differences between the two will be highlighted here.

Raised floor structure and basin

The raised floor structure differs between the two containers in terms of the placement of the profiles, as well as the type of floor panels. The FEG has metal grates in the center of the FEG, which function as a walkway for the crew, while still allowing air circulation between the sub-floor and the area above the floor. In contrast, the Service Section container has solid, laminate, plates.

Figure 1-12: FEG Container – Floor structure

Figure 1-12 provides an overview of the FEG raised floor configuration. The green line indicates the separation wall between the FEG and the Service Section. The pink dots indicate mounting points for the plant cultivation racks and the red squares indicate vertical structural profiles. As mentioned, the FEG floor has metal grates as floor panels in the central corridor. On both sides of the corridor there are no floor panels to allow fluid lines and power and data cables to easily route to and from the plant cultivation racks.

Separation wall

A separation wall has been built into the container close to the West-facing side of the container, see Figure 1-13. This wall isolates the FEG environment from the Service Section environment. Similar to the separation wall between the Cold Porch and the Service Section, there is a door and openings for air ducts, cable channels and fluid lines.

The door in this separation wall has a large window to allow crew to visually inspect the FEG without entering. A curtain is used to shield the Service Section from any light coming from the FEG.

Figure 1-13: Partition wall with door between Service Section and FEG

1.4 Container Interface design

The two containers which make up the MTF need to be connected together and sealed to separate the internal environment from the harsh Antarctic conditions. The containers will be mounted on twist locks which will be welded to a platform. Then the containers will be fixed together with 6 bolts, see Figure 1-14.

The gap between the containers is closed with a rubber seal, which will be covered by metal sheets on the outside. On the inside, the seal will be covered by insulation material, which in turn will be covered by high pressure laminate 'Trespa' plates. Approximately 260 mm space exists between the end of the Service Section raised floor and the Service Section to FEG separation wall when the containers are connected. Floor panels are used to cover the gap between the two container floor structures.

Figure 1-14: Overview of joint assembly between the two containers

2 Detailed design of the Service Section container

The previous chapter focused on the container structural design. In this chapter a brief overview is given of the internal configuration of the two containers.

2.1 Overall design

Figure 2-1 and Figure 2-2 are section-cuts of the internal Cold Porch and Service Section configuration. The cabinet in the Cold Porch is a free-standing structure, whereas the racks in the Service Section are all mounted to the profiles in the raised floor.

Figure 2-1: Section view of the internal configuration in the Service Section container (South side).

Not indicated in these two images are the panels which have been installed in front of the Nutrient Delivery System, Thermal Control System and the Atmosphere Management System, see Figure 2-3. These panels provide some noise reduction capability, to improve the crew working environment, and reduce the amount of dust and contamination which can enter the subsystem racks.

The harness (power and data cables) is routed through cable channels which are mounted against the walls and ceiling.

Figure 2-2: Section view of the internal configuration in the Service Section container (North side).

Figure 2-3: Internal view of the Service Section

2.2 Subsystem rack design

Note: The structural design of the ISPR is presented in a separate deliverable, focused on all aspects of the ISPR design.

The Nutrient Delivery System, Thermal System, Atmosphere Management System, the backup power system and the Command and Data Handling server computers are all installed in a Service Section rack built from 40x40 ITEM profiles.

The configuration of the subsystem rack can be seen in Figure 2-4 and Figure 2-5. The width of this rack is 600 mm, except for the section dedicated to the server computers. The width of the rack was fixed to ensure an adequate amount of corridor space in the Service Section for the crew to move and work.

Figure 2-4: Subsystem rack

To accommodate fluid lines, air ducts and power and data harness moving into and from the sub-floor area, there are no floor panels underneath the subsystem rack. Instead the rack is directly mounted to the structural profiles of the raised floor and plates were installed into the rack to provide support or mounting points as needed.

Figure 2-5: Subsystem rack configuration

2.3 Subsystem key values

The mass of the SS container was obtained from the load cell on the crane which moved the container into position at the beginning of the assembly and integration phase. At the time the mass was approximately 7100 kg.

This mass does not include the subsystem ITEM rack or the externally mounted components:

- Step ladder
- Roof access ladder
- Roof-mounted I-beams
- Roof-mounted safety railing

Furthermore, the weight of the Cold Porch storage cabinet, the crew working area and the subsystem rack cover panels are not included in the aforementioned mass.

The weight of these components is estimated to be around 400 kilograms, for a combined weight of roughly 7500 kg.

The structure and mechanisms subsystem does not have any power or data budget demands.

3 Detailed design of the Future Exploration Greenhouse container

3.1 Overall design

Error! Reference source not found. presents an internal view of the FEG. As mentioned, the central corridor has metal grates as floor panels. On either side, aluminum ITEM profiles have been used to create a multi-level rack system in which the plant cultivation trays can be positioned. Additionally, the ITEM racks provide the interfaces for the LED lamps, plant health monitoring cameras, the air ducts (at the back of the racks), and the various pipes and cable channels.

Figure 3-1: Internal view of the FEG container.

The ITEM racks are fastened to the profiles of the raised floor structure. Additionally, ITEM profiles near the ceiling span the corridor, connecting both sides of the FEG, to create one single ITEM structure.

3.2 Plant compartment rack design

The design for the plant growth racks within the FEG utilizes ITEM profiles, which are relatively cheap, lightweight and easy to assemble. The image in Figure 3-2 is an illustration of the proposed rack design. Standard 30 x 30 mm ITEM profiles were selected. These profiles were selected because they are big enough to allow for easy manual assembly, while being as lightweight as possible. Calculations done using the worst case load scenario indicate that these profiles provide sufficient load-bearing capability to support the plants and subsystem components.

Figure 3-2: FEG ITEM structure.

The FEG ITEM structure spans (nearly) the entire length of the FEG. It has four racks per side, and each rack has up to four levels. Two plant trays can be fitted per level per chamber, for a total of forty-two plant trays within the FEG.

The two sides of the plant compartment rack are connected with ITEM profiles at the top of the rack. These connecting profiles are one meter, to span the width of the corridor. The total width of the ITEM structure is 1940 mm, leaving 105 mm between the structure and the FEG walls, on both sides. This space allows for mounting of the air ducts and cable channels at the back of the ITEM structure.

Similar to the Service Section subsystem rack, this ITEM structure is mounted directly to the structural profiles of the floor, without any floor panels underneath.

Additional ITEM profiles were installed during the assembly and integration phase to provide additional mounting and fixation points for cameras and fluid lines.

3.3 Subsystem key values

The mass of the FEG container and the FEG ITEM structure was obtained from the load cell on the crane which moved the container into position at the beginning of the assembly and integration phase. At the time the mass was approximately 6400 kg. This mass already includes the main FEG ITEM structure, as depicted in Figure 3-2.

This mass does not include the externally mounted step ladder or safety railing, nor does it include some of the ITEM profiles which were added later. The weight of these components is estimated to be, at most, 50 kilograms, for a combined weight of about 6450 kg.

The structure and mechanisms subsystem does not have any power or data budget demands.

4 Operations

4.1 Nominal operations

During nominal operations no automatic or manual actions are needed to maintain either the container structures or the ITEM racks within the MTF.

Daily or weekly manual inspection of the interior and exterior will be used to identify potential off-nominal situations.

4.2 Off-Nominal operations

Off-nominal operations could include ice build-up around the external door(s), condensation at some point within the MTF or a change to the number of levels within one of the plant cultivation racks in the FEG.

4.2.1 Operator actions

- In case of ice build-up, manual removal of ice will be required.
- In case of condensation within the MTF, a video conference should be held to determine the best possible solution (e.g. reducing the humidity set point, adding insulation material.) Following this video conference, the operator needs to implement this solution.
- In case of a change in the number of levels in a plant cultivation rack, or an adjustment of the relative heights of the available rack, the operator will need to disconnect any piping and cabling interfaces, remove any loose and/or fragile components, loosen the mechanical interfaces, adjust the position of the ITEM profiles making up the level in question, refasten the mechanical interfaces, reinstall loose and/or fragile components and finally readjust the piping and cabling interfaces.

4.3 Maintenance and spares

Maintenance is limited to daily or weekly inspection. No spares are needed.

4.4 Preparation for shipment

4.4.1 Pre-shipment activities

Prior to shipment the containers will need to be decoupled, which requires the following actions (subsequent to any pre-shipment activities from other subsystems):

- Disconnect main power and data lines
- Remove externally mounted components
- Disconnect the piping and cabling connectors
- Disconnect and remove the flexible air ducts
- Remove rigid air duct sections
- Remove external panels and floor, wall and ceiling panels covering the container interface
- Remove bolts connecting the containers together

- Move first container onto flatbed, with crane
- Install cover plates on both containers to seal them for transport
- Install window cover plate
- Cover all openings in the container exterior (e.g. air inlet, main power line inlet)
- Move second container onto flatbed, with crane

4.4.2 In-situ assembly and pre-operations activities

- Lift containers onto platform
- Position containers and twist-lock mounting interfaces
- Weld twist-lock mounting interfaces fixed to the elevated platform
- Insert rubber seal between containers
- Fix containers together with bolts
- Cover exterior and interior of the container interface
- Remove covers on openings in the container exterior (e.g. air inlet, main power line inlet)
- Install externally mounted components
- Install rigid air duct sections
- Install flexible air ducts
- Connect the piping and cabling connectors
- Connect main power and data lines

5 Design lessons learned

A number of challenges were encountered over the course of the design and manufacturing process, which have been evaluated in order to provide guidance for future projects.

During the assembly and integration of the MTF, a number of problems arose with respect to installing, handling or removing certain components. For example, one of the bolts connecting the containers together was hard to access once the AMS air ducts had been installed, but the ducts could not easily be removed without first disconnecting the containers.

This, ultimately, resulted from the fact that the exact mechanism for joining the containers together had not been discussed early in the design process and as such had not been properly taken into account for the margin and clearance philosophy.

Additionally, the transport of the containers resulted in a slight 'twisting' (an angular deviation) of one container relative to another, which resulted in interference between the separation door to the FEG and the edge of the Service Section ITEM rack. While margin had been taken into account during the design phase, the 'twisting' resulted in deviations beyond the foreseen manufacturing tolerances.

As such, the following lessons should be learned for future projects:

- The assembly and disassembly steps, along with potential maintenance and repair activities, should be identified as soon as possible, in order to determine the potential impact on the design. In particular, dynamic envelopes should be defined (with margin) to ensure that there is sufficient space to carry out any of the previously mentioned activities.
- Increase the margins / clearance distances used within the structure (and configuration) design.

References

GK Marine, 2015. GK-Packsysteme - Packing Systems - Catalogue.

Trespa, 2015. Trespa TOPLAB Product Brochure G4700 version 1.2.

ITEM, 2015. ITEM Product Catalogue.

Figure A-2: Front, top and side views of the Elevated Platform

Figure A-5: Detailed drawing of Elevated Platform profiles (2)

Figure A-7: Detailed drawing of Elevated Platform support platform

Figure A-8: Detailed drawing of Elevated Platform walkway panels

Appendix A.2: Container Technical Drawings

EDEN ISS	Exterior Graphics: Container Wall 1	scale 1:20	LSG 13.01.2016
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EDEN ISS	Exterior Graphics: Container Wall 2	scale 1:20	LSG 13.01.2016
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Figure A-9: Mobile Test Facility Logo lay-out

Figure A-10: Mobile Test Facility – West-facing side

Figure A-11: Mobile Test Facility – North-facing side

Figure A-12: Mobile Test Facility – South-facing side

Figure A-13: Mobile Test Facility Logo – East-facing side

Figure A-14: Mobile Test Facility – Top view

Figure A-15: Mobile Test Facility – External components (1)

Figure A-16: Mobile Test Facility – External components (2)

Figure A-17: Mobile Test Facility – External components (3)

Figure A-18: Section views of Mobile Test Facility walls, ceiling and floor

Figure A-19: Service Section container - Separation wall

Figure A-20: Future Exploration Greenhouse container – Separation wall

Figure A-21: Waste and fresh water tank design

Appendix A.3: Service Section ITEM Rack Technical Drawing

Figure A-22: Service Section ITEM rack – isometric, front, top and left side views

Appendix A.4: Future Exploration Greenhouse ITEM Rack Technical Drawings

Figure A-23: Future Exploration Greenhouse ITEM rack – isometric view

Figure A-24: Future Exploration Greenhouse ITEM rack - front view

Figure A-25: Future Exploration Greenhouse ITEM rack – top view

Figure A-26: Future Exploration Greenhouse ITEM rack – section view (North-facing side)

Figure A-27: Future Exploration Greenhouse ITEM rack – section view (South-facing side)